

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

АНГЛО-АМЕРИКАНИЗМЫ В ЯЗЫКОВОМ ПРОСТРАНСТВЕ КАЗАХСТАНА

Чалимбаева А.Д.,

PhD докторант,

Туманова А.Б.

*д.ф.н., профессор кафедры русской филологии и мировой литературы
Казахского национального университета им. аль-Фараби*

ENGLISH-AMERICAN LOAN WORDS IN THE LANGUAGE SPACE OF KAZAKHSTAN

Chalimbayeva A.,

PhD student,

Tumanova A.

*d.p.s, Professor of the department of Russian Philology and World Literature
of Al-Farabi Kazakh National University*

Аннотация

Статья посвящена описанию особенностей функционирования англо-американизмов в языковом пространстве Казахстана в период последнего десятилетия XX в. и начала XXI в. Авторами определено активное употребление англицизмов и американизмов в сфере экономики и финансов на материале статей из СМИ РК, а также современных лексикографических словарей. В ходе исследования выявлены и описаны наиболее частотные англо-американские заимствования, используемые в современном русском языке Казахстана в рамках рассматриваемой сферы.

Abstract

The article is devoted to the description of the features of the functioning of British English and American loan words in language space of Kazakhstan during the last decade of the XX century. and the beginning of the XXI century. The authors determined the active use of Anglicisms and Americanisms in the field of economics and finance based on articles from the media of the Republic of Kazakhstan, as well as modern lexicographic dictionaries. In the course of the study, the most frequent British English and American English borrowings used in the modern Russian language of Kazakhstan within the framework of the sphere under consideration have been identified and described.

Ключевые слова: англицизм, американизм, заимствование, языковое пространство, сфера экономики и финансов;

Keywords: loan word, borrowing, anglicism, americanism, language space, economics and finance;

Introduction

As is known, one of the main examples of interlingual contact is the presence and functioning of the linguistic elements of one language in another. The most famous borrowed words are Anglo-Americanisms, the activity of which in the Russian language throughout the post-Soviet space especially increases in the period of the late XX and early XXI centuries. The most active functioning of Anglicisms and Americanisms is observed in the sphere of economy and finance of Kazakhstan, which determined the choice of the object of study in this article.

The purpose of the study is to identify and describe the Anglo-American borrowings (loan words) operating in the field of economy and finance of the Republic of Kazakhstan in the last decade of the twentieth century and at the beginning of the XXI century.

English is the language of international communication, it is widely used in various spheres of public life of the modern world community. This is facilitated by globalization, integration, a single information space, etc. As a result, in the vocabulary of any modern language there are different types of borrowings, the most

frequent of which are recognized as Anglicisms and Americanisms. First, let us turn to the definition of these terms based on lexicographic sources. The Oxford Dictionary gives a brief definition, in which «Anglicisms» are words or phrases of English (British) origin which are used in everyday speech of other countries, and «Americanisms» are words or phrases (expressions) typical to American English, which in turn are also borrowed by the recipient language from American English. [1]. It would be fair to also mention the definition of anglicisms in the book on the main concepts of linguistic terminology by R.L. Trask, where this term is given a brief concept that borrowings of this nature are words «copied» from English into another language for certain reasons [2, p. 136]. The concept of anglicism is revealed in more detail in the book on anglicisms by R. Fisher and H. Pulazhevskaya, in which it is commented that the term «anglicism», although it comes from the English language, is not necessarily always borrowed from British English as such, it can be borrowed from any version of the English language which exists today in many English-speaking countries [3, p. 8]. In the collection of monographs on

the use of anglicisms in European languages, edited by R. Hartman, scientists put forward several important criteria for this term: this type of borrowing should be recognizable by the English language from the lexical, morphological, grammatical and phonetic side, in which all words originating from closely related languages to English [4, p. 40].

In the dictionary of the modern American language, Americanisms are phonetic, morphological and lexical units which are special in the English language of the USA, which have a few deviations from the norms of the British literary language, or words or phrases that originated in the USA, but did not become widespread in the UK due to unique natural phenomena (names plants and animals characteristic of the North American continent, for example moose which is North American species), the characteristics of the life of the inhabitants of USA (drugstore which means «pharmacy», as well as «snack bar») [5, p. 88]. The concise dictionary of language contacts gives a relatively different definition of Americanisms, in which Americanisms are borrowings or «pervasions» from American English into different languages of the world, the flow of which has increased significantly in the past two decades, which is largely facilitated by the media (*shaping, briefing, know-how, slide, juice, teenager, jeans, crop-top, long-sleeve*, etc.) [6, p.57].

Speaking about the emergence of anglicisms in the recipient language, this type of borrowing must go through certain stages of adaptation, which include such stages as:

1. The initial stage – in which anglicism, according to R. Fischer, is like a kind of neologism [3, p. 8.], when it is still new and unknown to most speakers;

2. The second stage – in which Anglicism begins the process of incorporation into the recipient language and already takes part in institutionalization in the recipient language;

3. The third stage is characterized by the fact that the word gradually becomes part of the general «core» of the recipient language [7, p. 131].

Russian sources give more detailed definition for these terms: for example, in the explanatory dictionary A.N. Chudinov, «anglicism» from lat. Anglicismus is a kind of turn of speech that is characteristic of the English language [8, p. 35]. In the dictionary T.V. Zherebylo Anglicisms are words or their expressions borrowed from the English (British) language, while Americanisms are words or expressions of the American version of the English language, borrowed into other languages, including Russian. It is significant to emphasize that in the Russian language the most active source of borrowing foreign vocabulary into the Russian language is English, or rather, its American version [9, p. 107]. According to T.F. Efremova, also anglicism are turns of speech borrowed from the English language, built depending to a unique model and characteristics of it [10, p. 47]. It should be noted that not all scientists who define anglicisms give them basic characteristics, as, for example, D.S. Makhov defines anglicism as a kind of barbarism, an expression in some language, modeled on the English language [11, p. 81].

According to the linguistic dictionary T.V. Zherebylo, for the first time Anglo-Americanisms entered Russian language in the middle of the 19th century. Basically, scientists refer to them terms on shipbuilding, sports, economics, the names of some vehicles and the names of household items (dialogue, apartment, check, etc.). However, at the turn of the XX and XXI centuries the activity of promotion anglicisms and americanisms has increased significantly, in connection with new names have appeared relating to new designations: a) political processes, ideological realities, social structure (president, parliament, speaker, impeachment, consensus); b) economic, banking, financial, legal concepts (marketing, dumping, retailer); c) names associated with technology, automation, computer technology (computer, monitor, display, processor and its new varieties: intercom, shredder, scanner, tuner, toner, etc.); d) sports terms (layer, adviser, part-time, cricket, golf, etc.); names related to mass culture, art, music, show business (image, make-up, show business, beauty industry, etc.); 5) household and other areas (drink, barbecue, freeway, mail, release, townhouse) [9, p.107]. Words of everyday life were also borrowed, typical formulas of communication and interjections, including (for example: *hi, bye-bye, all right, big deal, ouch, oops, privatization, manager, thriller, killer, consensus, rating*, etc.). These are not only new single words, but also whole nests (for example: *bike, biker, bike show, superbike*, as well as *bikerism, biker*).

The study of scientific literature on this issue allows us to make a judgment that there is no single criterion, features and classification of English borrowings. Therefore, we can say that there are such types of Anglicisms as direct borrowings, hybrids, exoticisms, loan translations, foreign inclusions, parlangues and barbarisms, a detailed consideration of which is beyond the scope of this article. In our study, we will focus only on direct borrowings from the English language (Anglicisms) and from its American version (Americanisms).

Materials and methods

Linguistic analysis of anglicisms and americanisms in the modern discourse of the sphere of finance and economics was carried out on the basis of the study of scientific-theoretical and scientific-methodological information on the issues under consideration and on the basis of factual material taken from the mass media of the Republic of Kazakhstan: websites of republican newspapers and economic and financial journals «Business Kazakhstan», «Forbes Kazakhstan», «Kommerçant» and others. In addition, modern lexicographic dictionaries are also used: Dictionary of modern financial and economic terms A.I. Bazyleva, Modern Dictionary of Economics and Finance B.A. Raizberg, Dictionary of business terms E.S. Seriy, a reference edition of the economic dictionary of V.I. Nechaev. These sources are considered by us as illustrative material, which represents the modern business discourse in the field of economics and finance.

In the process of research, we studied 100 articles from the above sources. From the text of each article, using the method of continuous sampling, we collected fragments containing Anglicisms and Americanisms,

then they were subjected to careful study. In our work, we used such methods and techniques as the method of observation and description, generalization and systematization, comparison and comparison, analysis and synthesis, component analysis, statistical analysis, contextual analysis, etc.

The study was carried out in several stages of work:

1st stage: by methods of generalization, comparison, comparison systematized the use of terms;

2nd stage: quantitatively-statistical method revealed the most frequently used terms;

3rd stage: by carrying out vocabulary work, their main meanings were revealed;

4th stage: using the method of contextual analysis, we tried to determine the features of their use in real communication;

5th stage: summed up some results and conclusions of the work.

Next, we will dwell in detail on the description of each stage of the study and present the results obtained.

Results and Discussion

It is known that the lexical fund of the modern Russian language of the Republic of Kazakhstan, in this case, the business discourse of the sphere of economics and finance, consists of the following components: most of them are common normalized (or neutral vocabulary), general scientific terms (finance, economics, export, import), abstract nouns (collaboration, sponsorship, business, marketing), verbal nouns (payment, submission, withdrawal) and highly specialized words and phrases (schedule, outplacement, out-sorting, low-cost airline). On the basis of the material of the articles, using the method of computer calculation, we have identified the volume / number of language units in accordance with the types of the above discourse components in percentage terms. Thus, if the total amount of factual material is taken as 100%, then, accordingly, the commonly used vocabulary is represented in it in the number of units of the total number is 50%; general scientific vocabulary is 15%; abstract words are 13%; verbal nouns are 12%; highly specialized terms are 10%.

Further, as a result of the 1st stage of work, we identified 60 English (British)-American borrowings from the text of the articles, which, in accordance with their functional significance, were divided into 3 groups:

- Anglicisms and Americanisms used in the lexical system of the Russian language for a long time (before the reformation period): *economics, finance, import, export, currency, dollar, crisis, check, agent, partner, commission agent*, etc.;

- Anglicisms and Americanisms used in the lexical system of the Russian language relatively recently (late XX and early XXI centuries): *marketing, management, business, office, holding, consulting, investment, inflation, stagnation, recruiting, credit, deposit, broker, sponsor, top manager, office manager, investor, businessman, rating*, etc.;

- Anglicisms and Americanisms, which are relatively new in the lexical system of the modern Russian language, which we conditionally divided into two subspecies: mastered by native speakers and unmastered.

The first subspecies includes the following borrowed words of British-American origin: *voucher, valuation, devaluation, default, dumping, discount, offshore, tender, charter, barter, broker, dealer, realtor, etc. leasing, distributor, futures, franchising, franchising, merchandiser, startup, endowment, venture*, etc.

To the second subspecies: Anglicisms and Americanisms as highly specialized terms used and understood only in professional activities in the field of Economics and Finance, for example: outplacement, low-cost airline, outsourcing, outright, outtrade, warrant, vending, lockdown, retailer, networking, swap, schedule, actuary, etc.

At the 2nd stage of our work, using the method of social questioning (survey) and conducting a quantitative-statistical method, we identified vocabulary units of British-American origin, which are often used in the common vocabulary of native Russian speakers, such as: *barter, broker, dealer, realtor, agent, check, accounting, vending, voucher, swap*, etc. The respondents were students of Al-Farabi University of economic and financial specialties, PhD students and undergraduates from other specialties, as well as clients of first and second tier banks: retired people, workers and employees (without taking into account any national or age characteristics). The total number of respondents was 100 people. Of these, the majority of respondents chose as well-known (understandable in terms of meaning) words:

a) «a barter» is known by 91%, «a check» known by 92%, «an agent» known by 87%, «a broker» known by 78%;

b) and unknown (incomprehensible in meaning) words:

c) «an accounting» is known by 13%, «a voucher» is known by 4%, «an endowment» is known by 4%, «a vending» is 3%; «an actuary» is known by 2%, «a swap» is known by 1%.

At the 3rd stage we decided to consider the results of the social survey from the point of view of their description, presented in lexicographic sources, and try to find in the corresponding dictionary entries a reflection of the process of expanding, supplementing their meanings. In other words, in order to illustrate the mastery of these linguistic units, we present dictionary entries with a description of their meanings in lexicographic dictionaries. As an object for study, the following words were chosen from the established list of frequently used in common speech: *barter, lockdown* and from rarely used words: *retailer, networking, clearing, timeshare*. For example:

The term «a barter». This word is borrowed from English, where the noun «a barter» is defined as «barter trade» or «swap transaction». This word entered the Russian lexical-semantic system as a relatively special term in the economic sphere, which was initially registered only in terminological dictionaries and dictionaries of foreign words in economics and finance. For example, in the «Modern Dictionary of Foreign Words» the basic unit of interpretation is the phrase «barter deal», after which the lexeme of British-American origin «a barter» itself is placed. Nevertheless, the specified order of units subject to the concept testifies to the

fact that the dictionary unit «a barter» has not yet been fully assimilated into the Russian language. The interpretation of the above Anglicism is rather broad: «barter trade» or «a deal with a commodity exchange with the subsequent transfer of ownership of the necessary goods without financial costs» [12, p.48]. In the dictionary of the Russian language L.P. Krysin's definition is more lapidary: «a barter» means the exchange of goods without monetary participation [13, p. 62; p. 64].

The term «a lockdown». According to the dictionary of business terms E.S. Seriy anglicism, which recently came into Russian speech «a lockdown», and means «massive closure of enterprises or institutions and the cancellation of any events due to any adverse factors such as a pandemic, epidemic or other natural disaster». The English prototype of this new term consists of such parts as: «lock» + «down» with designations like: «lock» + «decrease». Accordingly, the newly minted term «a lockdown» means a decrease in the pace of public life through the closure of all institutions [14, Pp. 85-86]. It should also be emphasized that in Kazakhstan, English-American «a lockdown» has become widespread in the economic, financial and other spheres of public life in the era of the coronavirus pandemic. As a synonym in the system of the Russian language can be another term ««a quarantine» or the notorious «shelter-in-place restrictions».

An example of the use of this anglicism in the source we are studying:

«Ibex estimates its own insurance payments at \$7 billion to \$8.2 billion, and notes that the amount could be higher if the lockdown continues after the end of June» [15].

The term «a retailer». The term «a retailer» is an anglicism that should be differentiated from the similar by meaning verb «to retail», which comes from the British-English prototype. When it translated into Russian, it has such a meaning as: «distributive trades» or «home shopping service». In the explanatory dictionary of the information society and the new economy, the term «a retailer» is defined precisely as a company or firm that sells products or goods directly to consumer.

Examples of the use of this term in the source we are studying:

1. *«According to buyers in the market, the administration of Barys wholesale and retail market is considering the possibility of buying a large online retailer» [16].*

2. *«With SulPak having about 87 major electronics stores in Kazakhstan, Sulpak is another major retailer in the Kazakh market today» [17].*

The term «a networking». In the economic dictionary of V.I. Nechaev, the term «a networking» is a professional and social activity with complex tasks and business issues [18, p.463]. Its main function is to effectively solve, with the help of acquaintances and a circle of friends, both complex life tasks and business issues as quickly as possible. Difficult life tasks can include the following: for example, with the help of friends or their connections, arrange a child in an elite kindergarten in the city or, find a good job. The very essence of networking is as follows: the basis of net-

working is building long-term and trusting relationships with people and mutual assistance in interacting with these people.

Here are examples of the use of this anglicism in the source we are studying:

1. *«After the end of the official part, the guests will have a buffet table, and personal communication with the speakers of the meeting and business networking. All conference attendees will receive special gifts from Marino Madi and LoroPiana.» [19].*

2. *«The SEVEN Club has long been a club for communication between professionals in the field of information and its management: analytics, master classes, round tables, networking for clients, consumers and information systems experts.» [20].*

The term «a clearing». In the modern economic dictionary of B.A. Reisberg Anglo-Americanism «a clearing» is interpreted as the concept of «mutual settlements», which in essence is a cashless settlement between companies, countries, enterprises for securities and services rendered, goods sold or delivered to each other, sold by mutual offset, based on prepared conditions balance of payments [21, p.495].

Examples of the use of this anglicism and its forms in the source we are studying:

1. *«Depository and Settlement Company carries out clearing at the St. Petersburg International Commodity and Raw Materials Exchange» [22];*

2. *«The National Clearing Center is part of the structure of the Moscow Exchange and this clearing center is closely connected with the St. Petersburg Exchange» [23].*

The term «a timeshare». In the dictionary of business terms E.S. Seriy concept of «a timeshare» basically translated as «a type of ownership»; e.g. apartments abroad and in the economic and financial sphere as: «joint ownership of any real estate in a certain business with the possibility of using it for a specific period of time is directly proportional to the monetary contribution» [14, p. 85].

An example of the use of this anglicism in the source we are studying:

«For long weekends with excursions, they go to St. Petersburg, Moscow, Sochi, as well as to cities from the Golden Ring, which government agencies are gradually putting in order, - says Anna Vorontsova, president of the NPO Rustime for protecting owners of timeshare products» [24].

An analysis of the functional and linguistic assimilation of the above examples showed that all the Anglicisms and Americanisms we analyzed were borrowed using transcription and transliteration. Their adaptation and assimilation in the Russian language consists in the use in different case forms and genders of the modern Russian language.

At the 4th stage of the work, a contextual analysis was carried out, which was organized on the basis of newspaper and magazine articles presented in the discourse of the economy and finance of Kazakhstan. In the course of the study, the features of the use of Anglo-Americanisms related to the type «relatively new borrowings functioning in the Russian language» and their

subspecies are determined: as mastered (*venture, default, dumping, tender, endowment, start-up, leasing, franchising, etc.*) and unmastered (*outsourcing, net-working, lockdown, trader, retailer, etc.*) language units are highly specialized terms in real communication.

At the 5th stage of the work, the results were summed up.

As a result of the study, the features of the reflection of the process of expansion, narrowing and concretization of their meanings in the successor language were revealed. The results of this analysis gave reason to understand that vocabulary units of British-American origin are often borrowed more by the Russian language, due to such reasons as: the need to nominate new, previously non-existent concepts; trend towards internationalization; tendency to replace cumbersome phrases with one simple word.

The results of the study make it possible to reasonably say that Anglo-Americanisms in the Russian language system have different degrees of assimilation: some of them have been completely assimilated (management, marketing, office, business, crisis, partner, etc.), others have a relatively new status (briefing, consulting, holding, sponsor, rating, etc.), some of them are still only at the stages of development, in this process we have allocated conditionally: words-terms mastered and not mastered by native speakers.

Conclusion

Through this research, we came to the conclusion that the process of borrowing from the English language and its American version into modern Russian is currently intensifying; Since these sources are the basis for many professional languages, Anglicisms and Americanisms are widely used in youth slang. This process of borrowing is inevitable and is one of the brightest indicators of the development of any language in accordance with the pace of life, science and technology, with new realities in society. In this regard, the problem under consideration should always be in the center of attention of both linguists, teachers and language teachers, as well as an ordinary native speaker (in our case, modern Russian).

References

1. Oxford Dictionary of English. URL: <https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com> (accessed 26 April 2022).
2. Trask R.L. «Key concepts in Language and Linguistics». Edinburgh. Psychology Press Publishing, 1999. P.136.
3. Fischer, R., Pułaczewska H. «Anglicisms in Europe: Linguistic Diversity in a Global Context. Newcastle upon Tyne». Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2010. P.8.
4. Hartmann, Reinhard «The English Language in Europe». Oxford. Intellect Books Publishing, 1996. P.40.
5. Evans B., Evans C., «A dictionary of contemporary American usage», N. Y., 1957. P.88.
6. Pankin V.M., Filippov A.V. «Language Contacts: A Concise Dictionary». Moscow., publisher: Nauka. 2011. P.57.

7. Winter, Werner. «On Languages and Language»: The Presidential Addresses of the 1991 Meeting of the Societas Linguistica Europaea. Berlin. Walter de Gruyter Publishing, 2011. P.131.

8. Chudinov A.N. «Dictionary of foreign words included in the Russian language». St. Petersburg., publishing house V.I. Gubinsky. 1910. P. 35.

9. Zherebylo T.V. «Dictionary of linguistic terms» 5th edition. Nazran, publishing house: Pilgrim, 2010 P.107.

10. Efremova T.F. «Explanatory and derivational Russian dictionary». Moscow., Publisher: Prosveshchenie. 2000. P. 47.

11. Makhov D.S. «Borrowings in Russian». Moscow., publishing house «Prosveshchenie», 2003. P.81.

12. Bazyleva A.I. «Dictionary of modern economic terms». Tutorial. Minsk., Publisher: International University MITSO 2012. – p. 48.

13. Krysin L.P. «Explanatory Dictionary of Foreign Words». 6th ed. Moscow., publisher: EKSMO, 2005. Pages. 62-64.

14. Seriy E.S. «Dictionary of business terms». Moscow., publishing house Alliance Media, 1996. P.85.

15. Newspaper of Economics and Finance «Kommersant» URL: <https://www.kommersant.ru/doc/4343683> (Accessed April 28, 2022).

16. Republican economic newspaper «Business Kazakhstan» March 18, 2020 No. 11 (708) <https://www.dknews.kz/admin/arh/5e733291aa567.pdf> (Accessed April 28, 2022).

17. Republican economic newspaper «Delovoy Kazakhstan» April 24, 2020 No. 15 (712) URL: <https://www.dknews.kz/admin/arh/5ea20ffa62215.pdf> (Accessed April 28, 2022).

18. Nechaev V. I., Mikhailushkin P. V. «Economic Dictionary». Reference edition Krasnodar, publisher: Prosveshchenie-Yug, 2011. P.463.

19. Republican economic newspaper «Delovoy Kazakhstan» January 24, 2020 No. 2 (699) URL: <https://www.dknews.kz/admin/arh/5e2c737acd716.pdf> (Accessed April 28, 2022).

20. Republican economic newspaper «Delovoy Kazakhstan» December 20, 2019 No. 49 (696) URL: <https://www.dknews.kz/admin/arh/5dfc655e9e5c5.pdf> (Accessed April 28, 2022).

21. Raizberg B. A., Lozovsky L. Sh., Starodubtseva E. B. «Modern Economic Dictionary». 5th ed., revised and enlarged. Moscow, publishing house: INFRA-M, 2007. P.495.

22. Newspaper of Economics and Finance «Kommersant» URL: <https://www.kommersant.ru/doc/4242763> (Accessed April 29, 2022).

23. Newspaper of Economics and Finance «Kommersant» URL: <https://www.kommersant.ru/doc/3983269> (Accessed April 29, 2022).

24. Newspaper of Economics and Finance «Kommersant» URL: <https://www.kommersant.ru/doc/3983467> (Accessed April 29, 2022).